

Stabilising methane production in a series-stack of bioelectrochemical systems

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HIGHLIGHTS

- Diode-based CBS was tested in series BES cells performing electromethanogenesis.
- CBS mitigated voltage imbalance during hydraulic anode failure scenarios.
- CH₄ production and energy efficiency rose by 57 % and 49 % with CBS under anode failure.
- CBS enabled dynamic current redistribution, protecting bioanodes from damage.
- CBS allowed quick recovery post-feeding, showing robustness and scalability.

GRAPHICAL ABSTRACT

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ABSTRACT

Electromethanogenesis (EMG) is a power-to-gas technology that converts CO₂ into methane in bioelectrochemical systems (BES) using electricity. Scaling up requires the stacking of multiple BES cells, often through parallel and series connections. However, series configurations can lead to voltage imbalances due to biocatalysts variability and uneven feeding, compromising performance.

This work presents a simple, cost-effective cell balance system (CBS), based on commercial diodes, to equilibrate voltage across a three-cell BES stack performing EMG (2.7 V stack voltage). Cells were hydraulically connected in parallel and electrically connected in series. The stack was operated under normal and uneven anolyte feeding, with and without the CBS.

Without CBS, stopping the feed to one cell dropped stack voltage by 1.45 V and reduced methane production from 0.66 to 0.23 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹, while energy efficiency fell from 86 % to 44 %. With the CBS, voltage imbalances stayed below 1.15 V; methane production and efficiency increased by 57 % and 49 %, respectively, in

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comparison with the absence of CBS. The CBS redistributed the current, allowing a rapid recovery, after reestablishing feeding conditions.

In conclusion, a simple diode-based CBS provides a robust, scalable, low-cost means to manage voltage imbalances, facilitating reliable operation and industrial upscaling.

1. Introduction

Electromethanogenesis (EMG) is a power-to-gas technology that converts electrical energy and CO₂ into chemical energy (methane) using bioelectrochemical systems (BES) [1,2]. The oxidation reactions such as organic matter oxidation or water splitting generate protons and electrons at the anode compartment. Electrons flow through an external electrical circuit to reach the cathode, while protons and other cations migrate through the membrane (if used) to maintain charge balance within the cell [3]. At the cathode, methanogenic archaea act as biocatalysts, using electrons to reduce CO₂ to methane [4].

The EMG technology has the potential to convert rich CO₂ industrial off-gases into CH₄ [5,6] or for biogas upgrading [7] and can be integrated into the electricity grid for energy storage and grid balance [8,9]. These systems have demonstrated resilience to prolonged CO₂ starvation periods [10] and electrical fluctuations [11], making them particularly suitable for coupling with intermittent CO₂ emissions and/or renewable energy sources [4].

Stacking BES, which involves connecting multiple BES units, is considered an effective upscaling approach [8,12]. However, most BES stacks reported in the literature are electrically connected in parallel [13], operating at low cell voltage (1–3 V), incompatible with most industrial power applications that run at 24 V [14]. Series-connection can increase the stack voltage while reducing current, leading to lower ohmic losses and internal resistance, as well as allowing the use of thinner and cheaper electrical wiring [15]. However, industrial systems typically employ a mixed configuration, where the units are connected both in series and in parallel to balance voltage and current requirements. This approach improves energy efficiency and reduces the number of power supply units needed, resulting in additional economic savings [15].

A major challenge in series-connected stacks is the possibility of experiencing voltage unbalance between the individual BES, due to the biological nature of the catalysts. In series configurations, highly active bioanodes can drive the weaker ones beyond their optimal operating range, leading to unfavourable anode potentials during both start-up and steady-state operation [16]. In microbial fuel cells (MFCs) for electricity production, a large difference in voltage and reversed cell polarity (known as “voltage reversal”) can occur when using the series-stack connection, as a result of a non-spontaneous anode overpotential in a less-performing cell of the stack [16].

On the other hand, in series-connected stacks of electricity-consuming technologies, like electromethanogenesis cells, when these are pushed towards higher current densities, the risk of excessive bioanode potentials increases. Without efficient voltage management, excessive bioanode potentials can lead to irreversible biofilm damage, electrode material degradation compromising stack performance.

To mitigate voltage unbalance in stacked BES configurations, various control strategies were proposed in literature. Two main approaches exist for voltage balancing in systems that involve multiple cells connected in series: active bypass methods and passive bypass methods. The first ones rely on charge-shuttling components or voltage/current converters [15,20,21]. However, they are complex and impractical for small-scale systems, as they require multiple components like voltage controllers, magnets, and switches. In contrast, passive bypass methods employ semiconductor diodes to regulate voltage across stacked cells [16,19]. While several studies explored voltage reversal and control mechanisms in MFCs [12,17–20], fewer efforts were dedicated to electricity-consuming BES [15,16].

In the context of passive bypass methods, diodes act as electronic check valves, allowing current to flow only in one direction, once a threshold voltage is reached.

In this work, we present a passive, simple and inexpensive cell balance system (CBS) based on commercial diodes, costing approximately 1 EUR per diode unit. This novel system was applied to a stack of three BES cells performing EMG, to stabilise their voltage under fluctuating, realistic conditions such as hydraulic anode failure of one of the cells of the BES stack. To the authors’ knowledge, no previous studies investigated voltage balance in serially stacked BES using both bioanodes and biocathodes. The selected diodes were connected in parallel to each cell, acting as a passive bypass for the excess current which was destabilising the stack. The biocathodes performances were evaluated with and without the CBS, in terms of methane production rate, Coulombic and energy efficiencies, to validate the control system.

2. Materials and methods

2.1. Laboratory system setup and operation

Three double-chamber cells (179 mL anode chamber, 179 mL cathode chamber) were assembled in the laboratory. The cells are referred to as Cell 1, Cell 2, and Cell 3 throughout the document. The cathode chamber, with a cross-sectional area of 85 cm², was packed with stainless steel wool as cathode electrode (RAKSO Stainless Steel Wool Medium INOX 434, RAKSO, Germany). A titanium rod (6 mm Ø) served as current collector (GoodFellow, UK), providing an electrical connection to the external circuit. The anode chamber had an equal cross-sectional area. The anode consisted of four carbon fibre brushes (Mill-Rose, USA, total projected surface area of 214 cm²). An Ag/AgCl (3 M KCl) reference electrode (+208 mV vs Standard Hydrogen Electrode; Gauss Union, China) was placed in each compartment. The chambers were separated by a cationic exchange membrane (CMI-7000, Membranes International Inc., USA).

The electrodes were externally connected to a potentiostat (VMP3, BioLogic, France), that was used for their electrochemical operation and for monitoring the current, electrode potentials and voltage of each cell. A three-electrode configuration was employed, with the bioanode as the working electrode, the cathode as the counter electrode, and an Ag/AgCl (3M KCl) electrode as reference. The three BES cells were operated chronoamperometrically, setting the anode potential to –0.20 V vs Ag/AgCl [22]. After 30 days of cathode inoculation, the three cells were electrically connected in series.

During operation, fresh anolyte was continuously fed in parallel to each cell, through a multichannel peristaltic pump (HF-Lab, Hygiaflex, Spain), at a feeding rate of 2 mL min^{–1} with a hydraulic retention time (HRT) of 2 h. The feeding tank (1 L) was kept inside a water bath (Agibat-20, J.P. SELECTA, Spain) at 35 °C. No anolyte recirculation was applied at this stage. The anode circuit was maintained under anaerobic conditions and at atmospheric pressure. To improve the homogeneity of the anolyte within each chamber and reduce the development of substrate concentration gradients, recirculation was implemented from day 20 onward. The initial setup employed a low continuous feeding flow operating under laminar conditions, which provided limited convective mixing. The implementation of anolyte recirculation at a flow rate of 150 mL min^{–1}, significantly improved the homogenization within each chamber compared to the initial configuration. A schematic of the laboratory system is provided in supplementary information (SI) as Fig. S1.

The cathode chambers were hydraulically connected in series to a 2 L

recirculation tank, also maintained at 35 °C and in dark conditions. The catholyte was continuously recirculated at 200 mL min⁻¹ using another peristaltic pump (HF-Lab, Hygiaflex, Spain), while the recirculation tank was homogenised with a magnetic stirrer (350 rpm; MIXcontrol 40, 2mag, Germany). Pure CO₂ was introduced into the catholyte stream at 2.5 mL min⁻¹ using a flowmeter (AALBORG, USA), upstream of the first cell in the stack. This CO₂ injection resulted in an Empty Bed Retention Time (EBRT) of 1 h.

In-line pH and conductivity probes (HQ40 Multimeter, Hach Lange, Spain) provided continuous monitoring of the catholyte's pH and conductivity. The catholyte pH was maintained between 7 and 8 with occasional addition of HCl (5 M), if necessary. Conductivity was maintained below 25 mS cm⁻¹ through periodic catholyte replacement. The catholyte circuit was operated at an overpressure of 200 mbar by a non-return valve installed in the gas outflow line, with the pressure monitored by a digital indicator (PS42, E-MC, China). The gaseous stream volume leaving the cathodic compartment was quantified using a biogas flowmeter (Ritter MilliGascounter®, Germany) and collected into Tedlar® gas sampling bags (Supelco, USA) for volumetric composition determination.

2.2. Electrolytes and inoculum solutions

A synthetic medium was used as organic substrate in the anode chamber, mimicking a simplified wastewater effluent rich in readily biodegradable organic matter [23]. The medium contained: NaCl (0.45 g L⁻¹), MgCl₂ · 6H₂O (0.165 g L⁻¹), CaCl₂ (0.0136 g L⁻¹), Mg₂SO₄ (0.0153 g L⁻¹), NaHCO₃ (8.4 g L⁻¹), NaCH₃COO (2.5 g L⁻¹), K₂HPO₄ (0.128 g L⁻¹), NH₄Cl solution 1 M (0.925 mL L⁻¹), a trace element solution (1 mL L⁻¹), and Wolfe's vitamin solution (1 mL L⁻¹). The medium had an initial pH of 8.11, a conductivity of 11.34 mS cm⁻¹ and a theoretical Chemical Oxygen Demand (COD) of 1.7 g O₂ L⁻¹.

For the catholyte, an inorganic synthetic medium was used, modified from Ref. [24] simulating an exhausted wastewater effluent, nutrient rich yet low in carbon. Its composition included K₂HPO₄ (0.35 g L⁻¹), KH₂PO₄ (0.23 g L⁻¹), NH₄Cl (0.50 g L⁻¹), Na₂SO₄ (0.1 g L⁻¹), Na₂S · 9H₂O (0.5 g L⁻¹), CaCl₂ · 2H₂O (0.25 g L⁻¹), MgCl₂ · 6H₂O (0.41 g L⁻¹), NaHCO₃ (0.85 g L⁻¹), C₃H₈ClNO₂S (0.3 g L⁻¹) and the previously mentioned trace element and Wolfe's vitamin solutions (1 mL L⁻¹ each). The catholyte had an initial pH of 7.69 and a starting conductivity of 3.99 mS cm⁻¹. The detailed compositions of the trace element solution and Wolfe's vitamin solution are provided in Table S1 in SI.

The biocathodes were inoculated with a hydrogenotrophic methanogenic-enriched culture (1.8 L). This inoculum originated from the anaerobic digester sludge of the local wastewater treatment plant. The enrichment process was performed in 500 mL bottles and involved serial transfers of biomass to fresh catholyte (100 mL) at 30 % v/v intervals. The cultures were maintained at 35 °C under atmospheric pressure, with mild agitation and protection from light. A CO₂:H₂ (20:80 v/v) gas mixture was supplied weekly, connecting the headspace (400 mL) of the enrichment bottles with external 1 L Tedlar® bags containing the gas mixture.

The bioanodes were already inoculated before the experiment, obtained from previously operated BES cells in the laboratory. The inoculum source was the effluent of an established, acetate-fed laboratory-scale MFC, serving as a source of electroactive microorganisms. For inoculation, the effluent was mixed with an acetate-based medium in a 1:1 (v/v) ratio.

2.3. Electrochemical characterization and CBS integration in the series-connected stack

Once the three cells exhibited a steady-state behaviour, they were electrochemically characterised by means of polarisation curves. These were carried out using the potentiostat, applying sequential chronoamperometric steps of 20 min at different anode potentials, ranging

from open circuit up to +0.10 V vs Ag/AgCl, in 0.05 V increments. During polarisation curves analysis, the anode chambers of the cells were continuously fed with the acetate-based medium at a flow rate of 5 mL min⁻¹, reducing the HRT to 40 min and ensuring that the bioanodes were not substrate-limited. This characterisation allowed to identify the optimal operating point of the cells, in terms of energy efficiency and current density.

For the series-stacked configuration of the three cells, commercial diodes (UF5406-E3/54, Vishay, USA) were chosen, offering an average forward current of 3.0 A and a maximum forward voltage drop of 1.7 V. Specifically, two sets of 5 parallel connected diodes were installed in series one with the other, composing a "diode module" (Fig. 1 A). One diode module was installed in parallel to each series-connected cell (Fig. 1 B), for the following experiments with the CBS.

The diodes help stabilise the voltage across the stack by discharging excess current. Specifically, when the voltage drop across an individual cell of the stack exceeds the disruptive voltage of the diode, the diode provides an alternative path for part of the current, bypassing the underperforming cell [16]. This bypass prevents further cell voltage increase and protects the electroactive biofilm from damage.

However, this comes with a trade-off: when the cell voltage drops below the diodes' disruptive voltage, part of the current bypasses the cell and is dissipated as heat, leading to power losses [16]. To minimise unnecessary diode activation, the disruptive voltage of the diodes was selected to be slightly lower than the maximum voltage tolerated by the individual BES cells, ensuring that the bypass is triggered only when required. The electrical power loss associated with this bypass is quantitatively evaluated in this work.

After the electrochemical characterisation and diodes selection for CBS, the three cells were electrically connected in series and operated in chronoamperometric mode. Stack voltage and current were monitored and registered through the potentiostat, while individual electrode potentials and cell voltages were logged using an NI-USB-6212 data acquisition card (National Instruments, USA).

A series of experiments were conducted to simulate voltage unbalance conditions in the stack due to substrate limitation (Fig. 1 C, unprotected test). During the first hour of these experiments, the stack was operated normally. Then, a hydraulic failure of the anolyte supply was deliberately induced in each one of the cells, limiting its substrate availability. These failures were designed to replicate common operational issues in an industrial environment, such as a blockage in the hydraulic circuit. The hydraulic failure was maintained until the anode potential reached +0.50 V vs Ag/AgCl, to avoid prolonged exposure to potentially damaging conditions for the biofilm. Once the anode potential reached this threshold, the nominal anolyte feeding rate was resumed in the tested cell, restoring normal substrate conditions. This procedure was repeated sequentially for three cells in the stack. These tests are labelled as periods A-Cell1, B-Cell2, and C-Cell3, respectively (Fig. 1 C).

After completing this first set of experiments, the diodes modules comprising the CBS were installed in parallel to each cell. The experiments were then repeated with the CBS installed. The periods defined as D-Cell2, E-Cell3, and F-Cell1 correspond to sequential hydraulic anode failure tests induced in Cell 2, Cell 3 and Cell 1, respectively (Fig. 1 C, CBS test). Although the initial plan was to begin with Cell 1, the experimental sequence was deliberately altered, starting with Cell 2, followed by Cell 3, and finally Cell 1, in order to demonstrate that the order of testing did not influence their results. To ensure that neither electrochemical biofilm integrity nor methane production were compromised, an overnight recovery period was allowed between consecutive CBS tests. These recovery periods are shown in black in Fig. 1 C.

2.4. Chemical analysis and calculations

Liquid samples of anolyte influent and effluent were periodically

Fig. 1. (A) Diode module consists of two parallel-connected sets of five diodes in, which are subsequently connected in series. (B) Schematic diagram of application of the CBS to the cell stack; for clarity, each of the three diode modules is represented as single diodes. (C) Timeline outlining the complete experimental procedure (C).

collected for pH and conductivity analysis (HQ40 multimeter, Hach Lange, Spain) and COD determination (LCK 514 kits, Hach Lange, Spain).

The composition of the gas effluent collected in the Tedlar® bags was determined in terms of CH₄, CO₂, H₂, H₂S, CO, O₂ and N₂, by a gas chromatograph (490 Micro GC Natural Gas Analyser, Agilent, Spain) equipped with a dual-channel cabinet and a thermal conductivity detector. The CH₄ production rate was calculated by multiplying the volume of collected gas bag, measured using a Ritter MilliGascounter®, by its relative CH₄ content and dividing the result by the time it took to fill the bag (m³-CH₄ d⁻¹). This value was then normalised by the volume of the three cathode chambers (573 cm³), yielding the specific CH₄ production rate of the stack (m³-CH₄ m⁻³cathode d⁻¹).

A one-way analysis of variance (ANOVA) was performed using RStudio, to assess significant differences in current density among the three cells during inoculation, operation and characterisation periods. To identify specific group differences, a post-hoc Tukey's Honest Significant Difference (HSD) test was conducted. Statistical significance was determined at a p-value threshold of 0.05.

Coulombic Efficiency (%) was calculated as the ratio between the experimentally measured methane production and the theoretical one (Eq. (1)). The theoretical CH₄ production rate was determined based on the average electrical current.

$$\text{Coulombic Efficiency (\%)} = \frac{c \cdot F \cdot CH_{4,prod}}{V_m \cdot \int_{t_0}^{t_1} I dt} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

where *c* is the number of electron moles used to produce 1 mol of CH₄ (8 electrons), *F* is Faraday's constant (96485 C/mol), CH_{4,prod.} represents methane production, *V_m* is the molar volume of an ideal gas at standard laboratory conditions (24.45 L mol⁻¹), and *I* is the current (A).

EMG Energy Efficiency (η_{EMG}) was calculated by dividing the power content of the methane produced by the total power input to the stack, considering the Gibbs free energy of CH₄ oxidation (ΔG_{CH_4}), equal to 11 kWh Nm⁻³ CH₄ [25] (Eq. 2):

$$\eta_{EMG} (\%) = \left(\frac{CH_{4,prod.} \cdot \Delta G_{CH_4}}{I \cdot \sum_{i=1}^n E_{cell,i}} \right) \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 2}$$

In this equation, *E_{cell,i}* is the voltage of the *i*-th cell (V).

The electrical efficiency of the CBS (η_{CBS}) was calculated using Eq. 3:

$$\eta_{CBS} (\%) = \frac{P_{diode}}{P_{stack}} = \left(1 - \frac{\sum_i (V_i I_{diode,i})}{VI} \right) \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 3}$$

where *P_{diode}* represents the electrical power (W) that bypasses the cells through the CBS. *P_{stack}* represents the total power consumed by the cells stack (W). *V* represents the voltage applied to the BES stack (V). The term *V_i* refers to the voltage drop of the *i*-th cell (V) and *I_{diode,i}* is the bypass current through the *i*-th diode modules (*I_{diode,i}*). *I_{diode,i}* was calculated using the diode's characteristic curve based on ΔV_i , using the diode's characteristic curve (Eq. (5)).

When the CBS is in use, part of the input energy is lost in the balancing system. As a result, the effective system efficiency with CBS is calculated using Eq. (4):

$$\eta_{EMG,CBS} (\%) = \eta_{EMG} \cdot \eta_{CBS} \cdot 100 \quad \text{Eq. 4}$$

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Inoculation and operation

The three BES cells were operated using bioanodes pre-inoculated from a previous experiment. Stainless steel wool cathodes were introduced into the cells and subsequently inoculated for 30 days. From day 0 to day 20, Cell 2 showed a higher current intensity than Cells 1 and 3 (Fig. 2 A). A one-way ANOVA indicated significant differences among the three cells (*p* < 0.05). However, after analyte recirculation was introduced on day 20 (marked with a red arrow in Fig. 2), this difference decreased, although still remaining significant (*p* < 0.05).

The three recirculating cells (Figure S2 B, SI) displayed a similar current density distribution compared to the non-recirculating condition (Figure S2 A, SI). Once recirculation was applied, the average values of current densities became more aligned across the EMG cells, suggesting a reduced difference in response among them. Data dispersion was still slightly higher in Cell 2 but was less pronounced (Figure S2 A, SI). To further analyse these trends, the Tukey HSD test (Table S2 and SI) confirmed that, under recirculation, Cells 1 and 3 showed similar current density responses, while Cell 2 behaved differently from the others. Variability among EMG replicates is commonly seen when working with biocathodes [26]. Despite these variations, both the cathode potential (-1.1 V vs Ag/AgCl) and cell voltage (0.9 V) remained stable for all three EMG cells. The current density was approximately 2 A m⁻² for all replicates by day 30.

Fig. 2 B presents methane production from the EMG over the 30 days

Fig. 2. Evolution of current density (A m⁻²) and anode electrode potential (V) (A) and pH, conductivity and specific methane production rate, conductivity (B) for three replicate EMG cells operating at -0.20 V vs Ag/AgCl.

of cathode inoculation, showing a specific methane production rate exceeding 1 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹. After 1 day of operation, a peak in methane production of 1.06 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹ was observed, likely due to residual methane from the inoculum. Two days after inoculation, the system reached a maximum specific methane production of 1.51 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹. This maximum specific methane production is within the range reported in previous studies, where rates between 0.01 and 1.63 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹ have been reported in two chamber EMG laboratory setups with metal-based cathodes [27,28].

Subsequently, methane production decreased to 0.16 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹ on day 10. This drop can be attributed to the increase in catholyte conductivity rising from 20 mS cm⁻¹ initially to nearly 40 mS cm⁻¹ by day 14 (Fig. 2 B). This trend is likely due to the non-selective charge transport across the CEM, which transports cations from the anode chamber to maintain cell electroneutrality [29]. Excessive salinity can inhibit methanogenic activity, disrupting CH₄ production

[30]. To maintain conductivity below 25 mS cm⁻¹ the catholyte regeneration frequency was increased (shown by grey dashed lines in Fig. 2), leading to the recovery of specific CH₄ production rates up to 1.55 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹.

3.2. Electrochemical EMG characterisation and diodes selection for CBS

The three cells were electrochemically characterised using polarisation curves on day 23. Fig. 3 A presents the polarisation curves and the anodic half-polarisation curves of the three individual EMG cells. During this analysis, the catholyte pH and conductivity of the three cells were kept stable at 7.4 and 17 mS cm⁻¹. All three cells followed the same trend in current density evolution until reaching a cell voltage of 0.9 V, corresponding to an anode potential of -0.30 V vs Ag/AgCl (Fig. 3 A).

The semi-polarisation curves of the anodes (Fig. 3 A) show that the current density demand of the three cells evolved with a linear tendency

Fig. 3. (A) Polarisation curves of the three individual EMG cells, cell voltage (V) and applied anode potential (V) are reported as a function of current density. Purple-coloured zones shift in slope. (B) Characteristic IV curve of the tested diode module. (For interpretation of the references to colour in this figure legend, the reader is referred to the Web version of this article.)

with the applied anode potential, up to a saturation point which corresponds to a current density demand around 6 A m^{-2} , a cell voltage around 1 V and to anode potential between -0.30 and $-0.20 \text{ V vs Ag/AgCl}$ (Fig. 3 A). The change in the slope of current density in both polarisation and semi-polarisation curves (purple-coloured zones, Fig. 3 A) indicated that mass transfer, membrane pH gradients, or related physico-chemical effects are limiting the current [16]. The ANOVA test revealed no significant differences in current density among the polarisation curves of the three cells, with a p-value of 0.639. In view of stacking the 3 EMG cells, 1.0 V was considered as the optimum cell voltage (V_{sat}).

To integrate the CBS, the disruptive voltage of the diode (or diode module) should be slightly lower than the maximum voltage tolerated by each individual EMG cell in the stack [16]. To achieve this, several diode combinations were analysed based on their characteristic intensity-voltage (IV) curve. Fig. 3 B shows the IV curves of a line of two commercial UF5406-E3/54 diodes in series with five parallel diodes added to this arrangement. Two diodes in series was the only option that

allowed the disruptive voltage (indicated by a black arrow in Fig. 3 B) to approach but not exceed the specific requirements of the EMG cells (1.0 V).

With the diode module installed in the EMG stack, whenever one of the cells began to underperform (i.e. its voltage drop exceeding the disruptive voltage of the diodes), part of the current would be redirected through the diodes, effectively bypassing the affected cell.

By using the regression equation of the IV curve for two diodes in series and five in parallel, a sixth-degree polynomial trend line was extrapolated (Eq. (5)). The current distribution within cells and through the bypass diodes was calculated using Eq. (5) during the subsequent experiments. Furthermore, Eq. (5) was necessary to determine the CBS power efficiency, as calculated using the previously defined Eq. (3).

$$I_{\text{diode}_i} = -212.1 \cdot V_i^6 + 793.5 \cdot V_i^5 - 785.9 \cdot V_i^4 + 195.2 \cdot V_i^3 + 52.3 \cdot V_i^2 - 20.2 \cdot V_i + 0.93 \quad \text{Eq. 5}$$

Fig. 4. (A) Experiment with unprotected EMG stack (no CBS), operated at a stack voltage of 2.7 V. Evolution of stack voltage (V), current (mA) and individual voltage drops (V). (B) Evolution of anode and cathode potentials (V). (C) Evolution of the power consumed by individual EMG cells and total stack power (mW). Grey-coloured zones indicate the hydraulic anode failure scenarios (anode starvation).

3.3. Unprotected series-connected stack of EMG cells

An experiment was conducted to investigate voltage unbalance in the unprotected series-connected EMG stack. This test lasted for 4 h, with the stack voltage kept constant at 2.7 V (Fig. 4). According to the literature, in a series-connected stack of n BES cells, the total applied voltage should not exceed $n \cdot V_{\text{sat}}$ to maintain balanced individual voltage drops across each individual cell [16]. For this particular setup, the limit would be a stack voltage of 3 V. However, a lower stack voltage of 2.7 V (ideally 0.9 V per cell) was chosen for the experiment to simulate conditions similar to the electrochemical behaviour observed when cells were operated individually during EMG start-up.

During the first hour of the experiment (Fig. 4 A), current consumption remained stable at 80 ± 0.83 mA, and the potentials measured at the bioanodes stayed within a safe and stable range (< -0.20 V vs Ag/AgCl, Fig. 4 B). In addition, the individual voltage drops of each EMG cell remained well balanced during the first hour. These values refer to a steady-state operation of the stack of EMGs, i.e. no substrate limitation and no significant pH or conductivity gradient between anolyte and catholyte.

After this 1 h period, a hydraulic anode failure scenario was simulated per cell, following this order: A-Cell1, B-Cell2, and C-Cell3 (Fig. 4; grey-coloured zone). During the A-Cell1 period, the voltage drop of Cell 1 gradually increased, reaching 1.43 V after 24 min of anode starvation conditions (Fig. 4 A). This occurred together with the increase of the anode potential of the same cell to values higher than +0.45 V vs Ag/AgCl (Fig. 4 B), while the cathode potential remained near -1 V vs Ag/AgCl.

If this situation had persisted over time, it could have led to undesired reactions such as water electrolysis or other detrimental effects on the bioanode (e.g., microbial cell lysis). Prolonged exposure of the biofilm to positive potentials adversely affects its bioelectrocatalytic activity [10]. Additionally, this voltage imbalance caused a sharp decrease in current, down to 39 mA, indicating that the poor performance of Cell 1 was limiting the electrical current throughout the entire stack.

To minimise damage to electroactive anodic bacteria, an upper anode potential limit of +0.50 V vs. Ag/AgCl was set, corresponding to a voltage drop of around 1.50 V. This value was used as a manual safety threshold for each EMG cell during the unprotected series-connected stack experiment. When this threshold was exceeded, the feeding of all cells was re-established, allowing the system to return to its nominal operational state.

For the other two hydraulic anode failure scenarios, B-Cell2 and C-Cell3, the stack behaviour was very similar to that of A-Cell1. The cell subjected to the hydraulic anode failure experienced a higher voltage drop than the other two cells, 1.37 V for Cell 2 in B-Cell2 and 1.45 V for Cell 3 in C-Cell3 trials, while the stack current decreased to 44.3 mA (period B-Cell2) and 42.9 mA (period C-Cell3) (Fig. 4 A).

Restoring the cell feed prevented permanent damage to the anodic biofilm, allowing further experiments to proceed. The key indicators confirming that the bioanodes were not compromised during the unprotected series-connected stack test were the recovery of current levels to values similar to those recorded before the experiment (≈ 80 mA, see Fig. 4 A).

Electrolyte samples were collected from each cell and analysed before and after each anode starvation period. The catholyte pH remained relatively stable throughout the 4-h experiment (7.50 ± 0.03), in contrast, conductivity increased from 17.7 to 18.4 mS cm^{-1} over the course of the experiment (Fig. S3 and SI). This increase was attributed to the migration of cations from the anolyte to the catholyte through the CEM, as previously discussed. However, we assumed that this increase did not affect the EMG stack, as it remained within the salinity range inferred from conductivity values known to be tolerated by most methanogenic archaea [31].

The anolyte pH was 7.81 ± 0.08 during nominal operation

conditions. Interestingly, during A-Cell1, B-Cell2, and C-Cell3 periods, the pH was slightly more alkaline (around 8) for the starved cell (Figure S3 A, SI). On the contrary, anolyte conductivity dropped from around 10.8 to 10 mS cm^{-1} during A-Cell1, B-Cell2, and C-Cell3 (Figure S4 A, SI). On the other hand, the anolyte COD of the cells remained above $1.20 \text{ g O}_2 \text{ L}^{-1}$ during nominal operation. However, after A-Cell1, B-Cell2, and C-Cell3 periods, the COD level decreased below $0.75 \text{ g O}_2 \text{ L}^{-1}$ in the affected cell (Figure S4 B, SI). This indicates that voltage unbalance primarily resulted from substrate limitation, occurring when the substrate was unevenly distributed or insufficiently supplied to individual EMG cells in the stack. Without enough substrate for the oxidation reaction, the bioanode could not generate the required electrical current. In a series-connected stack, a substrate-limited anode behaves as if operating under constant current conditions, shifting its potential toward more positive values in search of alternative electron acceptors.

Regarding microbial activity on the cathodic side of the cell, the effect of temporary hydraulic anode failure in an unprotected EMG stack was evaluated in terms of methane production rate. Initially, the EMG stack exhibited a methane production rate of $0.66 \text{ m}^3\text{-CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$. During the first anode starvation period (A-Cell1), the rate dropped to $0.32 \text{ m}^3\text{-CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$, for period B-Cell2 the production rate was $0.24 \text{ m}^3\text{-CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$ and finally for period C-Cell3 it was $0.14 \text{ m}^3\text{-CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$, representing a 65 % average decrease. In terms of η_{EMG} it decreased from 86 % during the initial hour to 44 % after period C-Cell3 (49 % decrease).

Therefore, there was a direct negative impact on the electro-methanogenic activity of cathodic microorganisms, when one of the cells of the EMG stack was starving, i.e. lacking fuel. This was due to a reduced current availability of the stack, for in-situ H_2 production at the cathode (Fig. 4 A). Gas analysis showed that hydrogen did not accumulate in the cathode compartment throughout the study. H_2 acts as an electron carrier in indirect electromethanogenesis [24], therefore its decreased availability resulted in lower CH_4 production of the stack.

Re-establishing normal operating conditions, from 3.4 to 4 h, led to an increase of methane production, reaching $0.46 \text{ m}^3\text{-CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$. This suggests that 70 % of methanogenic activity was restored, compared with the initial value of $0.66 \text{ m}^3\text{-CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$. Although the recovery period allowed the perturbed cell and the stack to regain stable current, individual electrode potentials and cell voltages, methane production data indicated that this duration may not have been sufficient for full methanogenic reestablishment. To achieve full recovery, the system was let operate at normal conditions overnight.

Overall, maintaining a constant stack voltage while the anolyte of an individual EMG cell of the stack is depleted leads to cell voltage and electrode potential distortions and a reduction in electromethanogenesis activity. However, if anode starvation lasts only a few minutes, microbial activity appears to partially recover.

3.4. Evolution of EMG cell stack with CBS

A second set of tests was conducted with the CBS installed in parallel to the EMG stack, preventing voltage unbalance and ensuring a stable operation. This experiment was referred to as CBS test and was carried out over three consecutive days, maintaining a constant stack voltage of 2.7 V (Fig. 5). Each day, one cell in the stack was subjected to a hydraulic anode failure scenario for 6 h (D-Cell2, E-Cell3, and F-Cell1). Therefore, this experiment aimed to assess CBS effectivity in protecting the EMG stack and anode starvation caused by a hydraulic failure over a longer period of time. After the 6 h starvation period, the stack was returned to normal operating conditions overnight, allowing a complete EMG system recovery.

Fig. 5 A shows that the CBS effectively balanced the voltage drops of the three cells during a simulated hydraulic anode failure scenario (E-Cell3). During E-Cell3, Cell 3 voltage increased from 0.94 V to 1.15 V and remained stable at this value for the subsequent 6 h. In a series-

Fig. 5. E-Cell 3 experiment. (A) Evolution of voltage drops and electrical current, operated at a stack voltage of 2.7 V. (B) Evolution of the potentials of anode and cathode. (C) Evolution of the power consumed by individual EMG cells and total stack power (mW). Blank zones indicate no-substrate limited operation conditions and coloured zones indicate hydraulic anode failure.

stack, the current is equal to the maximum current of the least performing cell [15], which is the cell experiencing the highest overpotential (Cell 1 during the first hour of experiment in Fig. 5 A). When the anode was not being fed, the current dropped from 78.86 ± 1.36 mA to 57.81 ± 5.93 mA and remained stable at this value for the following 6 h of anode starvation. Once the feed was restored, the current returned to its pre-starvation level (73.15 ± 0.98 mA).

Therefore, the performance drop of an individual EMG cell affected the other two cells only minimally, thanks to the CBS, while simultaneously causing a rise in anode potential from a stable and safe value of approximately -0.42 V vs. Ag/AgCl to a slightly positive but still acceptable working potential of $+0.29$ V vs. Ag/AgCl (final registered value at 7 h) (Fig. 5 B). The feed-connected EMG cells (Cell 2 and Cell 3) maintained the anode potentials at -0.40 V vs. Ag/AgCl.

Similar trends were observed in tests D-Cell2 and F-Cell1 (Figures S5–S6, SI). In D-Cell2, the current initially measured 78.9 ± 3.4 mA, dropped to 56.5 ± 9.1 mA, and later recovered to 69.3 ± 6.5 mA. During anode starvation, Cell2 voltage rose from 0.97 V to 1.13 V, while its anode potential increased to $+0.29$ V vs. Ag/AgCl after 7 h. In F-

Cell1, current decreased from 78.9 ± 1.4 mA to 68.7 ± 3.5 mA during starvation and recovered to 77.4 ± 3.5 mA upon feed restoration. Cell1 voltage increased from 0.96 V to 1.12 V and remained stable, with its anode potential staying around $+0.25$ V vs. Ag/AgCl throughout the period.

The individual voltage drops of the series-connected EMGs never exceeded the safety threshold of 1.50 V. The diode modules allowed current to bypass through the substrate limited cell. The CBS dynamically maintained the set voltage, thereby protecting the microorganisms at the bioanode from destructive electrode potentials. Although no significant loss of electroactivity was observed in the cells after the experiment, prolonged exposure (21–90 days) to no-feeding conditions would eventually damage the anodic biofilm due to starvation. This disruption may be reversible [32] but it inevitably affect biofilm composition and/or the involved electron transfer pathways within a single organism, making a functionally different anodic biofilm [10].

Catholyte and anolyte samples were collected and analysed before and after each anodic starvation period. The catholyte pH remained stable between 7.3 and 7.4 throughout the 8-h experiment, with

minimal variation (Fig. S7 and SI). Catholyte conductivity increased from 18 mS cm^{-1} to 22 mS cm^{-1} over three days during the CBS experiment (Fig. S7 and SI), but this did not significantly affect methanogenic activity, with methane production rates staying between 0.65 and $0.72 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$. The anolyte pH remained close to 8 throughout the experiment, regardless of whether the system corresponded to D-Cell2, E-Cell3, or F-Cell. Its conductivity dropped from 10 to 11 mS cm^{-1} to about 9 mS cm^{-1} after hydraulic anode failure (Figure S8 A, C, and E, SI). After refeeding the system at hour 7, conductivity returned to the initial range due to the replacement of the exhausted anolyte.

All three EMG cells subjected to hydraulic anode failure (D-Cell2, E-Cell3, and F-Cell1) exhibited a COD concentration below $0.75 \text{ g O}_2 \text{ L}^{-1}$, approximately 30 min after the onset of hydraulic anode failure (Figure S8 B, D, and F, SI). This COD value corresponds to the same COD concentration reported in the unprotected trial, where the system was in a substrate-limiting condition. It indicates that EMG cells experiencing hydraulic anode failure were subjected to substrate limitation.

The effect of the anodic starvation test on specific methane production and Coulombic efficiency with the proposed CBS integrated into the EMG stack is presented in Fig. 6 A. During E-Cell3 operation, the methane production rate exhibited a decreasing trend, from $0.72 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$ until reaching a final methane production rate of $0.43 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$. The average decrease in terms of methane production taking into consideration the three CBS test was 45 % (Fig. 6 B). This trend is also reported in terms of energy efficiency ($\eta_{\text{EMG,CBS}}$), the $\eta_{\text{EMG,CBS}}$ dropped from 83 % to 66 %. Even so, by implementing the CBS in the stack a 57 % increase in methane production and 49 % improvement in energy efficiency is achieved compared to the results obtained in the unprotected stack.

Following the reestablishment of non-limiting operating conditions after 6 h of starvation, methane production did not exhibit an upward trend in E-Cell3. After overnight recovery, methane production values recovered to $0.65 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$, marking the completion of the E-Cell3 experiment.

However, in periods D-Cell2 and F-Cell1, after 6 h of starvation, methane production showed an upward trend upon reestablishing non-limiting operating conditions, reaching 0.54 and $0.41 \text{ m}^3 \cdot \text{CH}_4 \text{ m}^{-3} \text{ cathode d}^{-1}$, respectively (Figure S9 A and B, SI). During two out of three hydraulic anode failure periods with CBS (D-Cell2 and F-Cell1), the stack exhibited a partial recovery of methane production within 1 h,

with 83 % and 63 % restoration, respectively. In all cases, a full (100 %) methane production recovery was achieved after letting the system operate at normal conditions overnight. Cristiani et al. suggested that for starvation periods lasting over 90 days in EMG cells, methanogenesis can be severely affected and the biocathode would require more time to regain activity, as the methanogenic microorganisms are thermodynamically disadvantaged due to their anaerobic nature [10].

The CBS enabled the three-cell stack to operate for 6 h without feeding one of the cells, while maintaining a 57 % higher methane production rate than the system without CBS.

While the CBS was effective in balancing the voltage and preventing the sharp decrease in methane production when a hydraulic anode failure was forced, it had a drawback. Voltage drops exceeding the diodes' disruptive voltage allowed part of the current to bypass the cell, resulting in energy loss as heat. With the CBS, each individual EMG cells in the stack draw a different amount of current relative to the activity of the bioanode and simultaneously bypassing the surplus current back into the circuit. This bypass current of cell ($I_{\text{diode}i}$) could be calculated through its voltage drop (ΔV) using Eq. (3). This way, it was possible to evaluate the current distribution within EMG cells and bypass diodes (Fig. 6 B).

The bypass current was consistently higher for the cell experiencing substrate-limiting conditions. Interestingly, under no-limited conditions—before any hydraulic anode failure was applied (first hour of the experiment)—the current distribution followed the same pattern for D-Cell2, E-Cell3, and F-Cell1. Specifically, the bypass current for Cell 1 was 13 % higher than for Cells 2 and 3 % than for Cell 3. This was because, in this case, Cell 1 was the lowest-performing cell on the stack (see Fig. 3).

The power efficiency of the proposed CBS was strongly influenced by the diode module used in the bypass line and the individual cell voltages, resulting from the applied stack voltage. By properly configuring these two parameters, the EMG stack could achieve high-power efficiency while operating at normal conditions ($\eta_{\text{CBS}} = 91 \%$). During hydraulic anode failure period E-Cell 3, the bypass diode of Cell 3 was activated, redirecting part of the current outside the cell (Fig. 6 B). After 2 h without feed, less than 5 % of the total current was flowing through Cell 3, reducing the CBS power efficiency to approximately 60 %. The lowest η_{CBS} value during Cell 3 starvation was recorded after 6 h of no feeding, dropping to 42 %. Similar behaviour was observed during anode starvation in period F-Cell1 (Figure S10 B, SI). In the case of D-Cell2, it took

Fig. 6. (A) Cathodic Coulombic efficiency (bar plot) during anodic hydraulic test E-Cell3 when adopting the proposed CBS and evolution of specific methane production rate (scatter plot). The 5 h sample was excluded due to air infiltration into the Tedlar® sampling bag, leading to contamination. (B) Distribution of electrical current across the three series-connected EMG cells and bypass diode modules.

Fig. 7. Comparative analysis of specific methane production rate (A), total stack current (B), and energy efficiency (C) of the EMG system operated at normal conditions, with and without the CBS. The figure shows the average values with associated standard deviations obtained from the three replicate cells for each condition.

3 h of starvation for the cell to be completely “deactivated”, meaning that all the current available was bypassed through the diode line on this cell (Figure S10 A, SI). In all cases, the disconnected EMG cells dropped to nearly 0 mA of current after 4 h of the experiment, while the feed-connected EMG cells continued consuming current.

Adopting diodes as a CBS enabled the independent operation of the three EMG cells in the series-stack, allowing each to utilize the optimal current from the substrate while bypassing excess through the diodes. It effectively stabilised cell voltages, prevented bioanode damage, and electrically decoupled the underperforming EMG cell due to anolyte substrate limitations. As a result, cells could be replaced without disrupting the rest of the stack, as the current was redirected through the bypass line.

Once the feed was reestablished, the initial current distribution was almost fully recovered in 1 h. Consequently, η_{CBS} recovered high values, in all cases (>87 %). The continuous supply of fresh medium to the anodes helped maintain a balanced voltage drop within the EMG stack, effectively limiting excess current flow through the bypass diodes and ultimately allowing the system to work at high values of CBS power efficiency.

Fig. 7 presents the average results from the three cell replicates, comparing the specific methane production rate, current, and energy efficiency of the EMG system under normal feeding conditions and during hydraulic anode failure, both with and without the CBS.

In the absence of the CBS, interrupting the feed to one cell led to a drop in current from 80 mA to 42 mA, a reduction in methane production from 0.66 to 0.23 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹, and a decrease in energy efficiency from 86 % to 44 %.

When the CBS was applied under the same failure condition, methane production reached 0.37 m³-CH₄ m⁻³ cathode d⁻¹, current remained at 61 mA, and energy efficiency only decreased to 66 %.

This represents an improvement of ~57 % in methane production ~46 % in current consumption and ~49 % in energy efficiency compared to the system without CBS during hydraulic failure.

4. Conclusions

In this work, a passive, easy-to-apply, and low-cost CBS based on commercial diodes was implemented for the first time in a serially connected stack of three BES cells performing EMG. The CBS ensured voltage stabilisation throughout the operation during anode starvation periods, preventing individual cells from exceeding a critical voltage drop of 1.50 V. This permitted continued operation while avoiding irreversible anodic biofilm damage. In unprotected stacks, the lack of substrate in a single cell rapidly led to voltage unbalance, causing methane production and η_{EMG} to decrease by 65 % and 47 %, respectively. However, with the CBS installed, specific methane production decreased by only 40 % after 6 h of starvation, and $\eta_{\text{EMG,CBS}}$ showed a 16 % drop, representing 1.6 times higher methane production and 15 times

longer operational stability compared to the unprotected EMG stack.

Furthermore, the diodes allowed current redistribution through the cells, dynamically adjusting to variations in individual cell performance while maintaining the CBS’s power efficiency above 42 % under starvation conditions. Once normal feeding conditions were restored, CBS power efficiency rapidly recovered to over 87 %, demonstrating the system’s robustness and resilience.

Beyond ensuring stable operation, the CBS enhances the scalability of BES stacks by allowing higher applied voltages, closer to those required for industrial applications, where voltage balancing is essential to optimise efficiency and durability. Its compatibility with mixed series and parallel configurations, commonly used in industrial systems, further reinforces its relevance for scalable BES applications. Its simple design allows adaptation to various BES technologies, enhancing system stability and methane production even under fluctuating conditions. By minimising cell differences, particularly with complex matrices like wastewater, the CBS proves valuable for real-world applications. Future studies should evaluate its long-term performance in larger systems and real wastewater environments.

CRediT authorship contribution statement

Maria Vega-Paredes: Writing – original draft, Visualization, Validation, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Data curation, Conceptualization. **Daniele Molognoni:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Project administration, Methodology, Funding acquisition, Conceptualization. **Simone Colantoni:** Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation, Formal analysis, Conceptualization. **Pau Bosch-Jimenez:** Writing – review & editing, Funding acquisition. **Sebastià Puig:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision. **Eduard Borràs:** Writing – review & editing, Supervision, Resources, Project administration, Funding acquisition.

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Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that this work was conducted in the absence of any commercial or financial relationships that could be construed as a potential conflict of interest.

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Glossary

BES	Bioelectrochemical system
CBS	Cell balance system
COD	Chemical oxygen demand
EMG	Electromethanogenesis

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jpowsour.2025.238119>.

Data availability

The dataset corresponding to this paper has been published in Zenodo repository, with DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15275012.

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